

Original article

GENERALIZED RANDOM FOREST FOR PREDICTIVE MODELING AND CAUSAL INFERENCE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY WITH TRADITIONAL APPROACHES

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Abstract: This paper provides a theoretical review of predictive modeling by utilizing traditional methodologies and introduces a novel approach, Generalized Random Forest (GRF), as an alternative method that also serves as a complementary tool for causal inference and estimating treatment effects. Conventional techniques such as Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) are explored in terms of predictive capabilities, causal relationships, and internal features, determining how their underlying mechanisms, use cases, and limitations differ from the GRF method. In order to support the robustness and the validity of the results, the comparison is conducted using three benchmark datasets from the PLS-SEM literature – TAM (Technology Acceptance Model), CUSL (Corporate Reputation Model) and UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology). The analysis focuses on the potential of GRF to produce results similar to traditional methods, while also providing additional insights through its advanced procedures for modeling data-driven heterogeneity, estimating conditional treatment effects, and refining mechanisms in prediction algorithms. By incorporating features such as heterogeneous treatment effect estimation, non-linear relationship modeling, and adaptive weighting using observation similarity, GRF turns into a valuable tool for informed decision-making based on rich data structures by revealing critical behavioral drivers across customer segments and by designing targeted policies. Thus, GRF holds strong potential in economic research, where understanding heterogeneous responses and complex causal relationships across diverse populations becomes essential.

Keywords: Predictive Modeling, Partial Least Squares, Generalized Random Forest, Multiple Linear Regression, Heterogeneous Treatment Effects

JEL classification: C18, C14, C13

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1. Introduction

Predictive modeling has traditionally utilized methods such as Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) and Random Forest (RF) as foundational approaches, depending on the type of research problem and the dataset involved. This study aims to compare the techniques in terms of their predictive modeling and variable importance algorithms, while also evaluating their ability to answer research questions in a similar manner. The proposed comparative approach not only aids in comprehending the efficacy of each methodology but also offers insights to their distinct strengths and advantages, particularly in addressing complex relationships within the data.

By exploring a range of traditional techniques, this analysis seeks to determine if Generalized Random Forest, a particular case of Random Forest, can provide enhanced solutions, especially in situations when causal analysis is required. The new functions introduced by this method will be thoroughly described, uncovering their practical use and contribution to predictive performance and interpretability. Causal inference will be explored through the use of GRF, with its ability of handling heterogeneity and assessing treatment effects, extending beyond standard variable-target associations.

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These capabilities offer new perspectives into research questions, improving the understanding of variable interaction, leading to more advanced conclusions and accurate predictive models. Through its methodological advancement, GRF defines its role in assisting economists attempting to study and analyze consumer behavior and sub-group interactions. In light of its wide applicability, GRF also serves as a solution for strategic planning and resource allocation, by aligning with customer needs and maximizing the effectiveness within diverse market segments.

2. GRF Methodology

Generalized Random Forest (GRF) represents an extension of the Random Forest algorithm, developed approximately 20 years later after the introduction of the standard version. As described in CRAN, the original source of the package (R Core Team, 2024), GRF is a non-parametric method, primarily used for estimating data relationships with an increased focus on heterogeneous treatment estimation. It is suitable for cases when variations are present across different groups formed inside a dataset, while also supporting diverse regression types, including least-squares, quantile, and survival, tailored to the specific needs of the research context (Athey, et al., 2019). While a significant part of the standard Random Forest algorithm is preserved, GRF introduces several changes in the estimation process, such as local adaptive weights and heterogeneous treatment effect estimation, ensuring enhanced flexibility in addressing novel applications in causal inference.

2.1 Foundation in Random Forest

Random Forest methodology (Breiman, 2001) utilizes multiple Decision Trees for predictive modeling, which represent a non-parametric method that organizes data hierarchically, recursively partitioning it based on relevant features, using a Greedy approach for optimal splits (Dijkstra, 1959). Rather than building a single tree and rely on its result for prediction, ensemble methods consider multiple trees, trained on distinct datasets generated using a Bootstrap technique (B. Efron, 1979) where samples are drawn with replacement. The individual predictions are combined using an aggregation method such as majority voting or averaging. This approach mitigates overfitting by introducing variation among trees, reducing the likelihood of generating overly similar trees, thereby ensuring the robustness of the final model.

2.2 Splitting and Prediction Algorithm

Both Random Forest and Generalized Random Forest rely on recursive partitioning, ensemble techniques and random feature selection. The differences lie in the prediction process as GRF replaces the simple averaging with a weighted average procedure based on heterogeneous effects, known as adaptive nearest neighbor method. The algorithm starts with identifying the terminal nodes known as leaves and group similar instances as neighbors. Weights are assigned by how frequently each neighbor appears in the same leaf across all trees, influencing the final prediction.

Another notable distinction in GRF is represented by its splitting methodology which aims to maximize variance across the nodes and focuses on how treatment effect influences the predictions. Table 1, extracted from (Athey, et al., 2019) exemplifies this process, where each tree-training sample pair determines whether the test instance falls into the same leaf.

Table 1: Weighted Prediction Approach in GRF

Training Sample	Tree 1	Tree 2	Tree 3	Count Yes	Similarity Weight for x: $\alpha(x)$	Y (Outcome)	$\alpha * Y$
X1	Yes	No	Yes	1/3 + 0 + 1	4/9	4	16/9
X2	No	No	No	0 + 0 + 0	0	-0.5	0
X3	Yes	No	No	1/3 + 0 + 0	1/9	2	2/9
X4	Yes	Yes	Yes	1/3 + 1 + 0	4/9	4	16/9
Final Prediction							34/9

Source: (Athey, et al., 2019)

Based on the matches, a Boolean flag is introduced, and similarity weight is calculated by normalizing the total number of “Yes” flags across the trees. Formally, the similarity weight measurement for a test instance x is computed as:

$$\alpha(x, T_i, X_j) = \frac{1}{|L(T_i, x)|} \tag{1}$$

where T_i is the tree being analyzed, and $L(T_i, x)$ represents the number of training samples that share the same terminal node as training sample X_j . The overall similarity weight across the trees is then averaged:

$$\alpha(x, X_j) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B \alpha(x, T_i, X_j) \tag{2}$$

For the final prediction Y_j , a weighting procedure is performed with the previously resulted scores as:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \alpha(x, X_j) \cdot Y_j \tag{3}$$

2.3 Causal Inference

A primary use case of GRF involves estimating Conditional Average Treatment Effects (CATE), shifting from standard prediction to understanding causal effects. It evaluates how the presence of a treatment influences the outcome for specific groups by quantifying the effect across the dataset. On top of estimating personalized treatment effects, GRF computes the average treatment effect for the entire population using a doubly robust estimator, refining the simpler general approach which averages the treatment effects. This method allows for the estimation of the average treatment effect for treated versus control groups and evaluates the overlap between them by granting more weight to individuals with similar chances of receiving treatment or not.

2.4 GRF Forests

GRF framework includes various specialized forests, tailored to tackle specific use cases, such as survival forest for time-to-event predictions, multi-task forest for predicting multiple related outcomes and instrumental variable forests for handling endogeneity on biased datasets. However, regression and causal forests are the most commonly used. Causal forests monitor the impact of a treatment across different population segments, while setting causal inference as the primary objective. It studies the cause-and-effect relationship between an intervention and an outcome, estimating heterogeneous treatment effects instead of just emitting predictions. Regression forest reprioritizes towards predictions instead of causal inference, thereby aligning to the standard Random Forest as it estimates the expected outcome instead of the conditional average treatment effect.

2.5 Variable Importance

GRF package provides a built-in functionality for the importance of variables, extended from the traditional Random Forest Algorithm, that identifies the most significant features and ranks them according to their contribution to the model predictions (Athey, et al., 2019). The formal definition of variable importance (Nakamura, 2023) evaluates the increase in prediction error when a feature $X(j)$ is excluded.

$$VI(X(j)) = \int \left[\left(y - \widehat{f}^{RF}(x_{(-j)}) \right)^2 - \left(y - \widehat{f}^{RF}(x) \right)^2 \right] f_{X,Y}(x,y) \, dx \, dy \tag{4}$$

\widehat{f}^{RF} : Prediction with all features; $\widehat{f}^{RF}(x_{(-j)})$: Prediction excluding feature $X(j)$

Since the procedure runs once for the entire set of variables and again for each excluded feature, the algorithm becomes computationally intensive. To address this, Permutation-Based and Tree Randomization-Based Variable Importance are introduced to ensure unbiased error estimates without extensive refitting by relying on Out-Of-Bag (OOB) data for validation. The first method shuffles feature values to measure accuracy drops, while the second alters the tree structure to gauge feature contribution for the target variable. In GRF, variable importance is assessed using Mean Decrease in Impurity (MDI) or Mean Decrease in Accuracy (MDA). MDI tracks the variables that reduce node impurity, whereas MDA checks the accuracy reduction caused by feature selection, where a larger reduction indicates a more significant feature.

3. PLS-SEM Methodology

Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) appears as a widely used method for analyzing complex relationships between variables that can be directly observed and latent variables, also known as constructs, which cannot be directly measured (Hair, et al., 2021). The modeling process starts with defining the PLS path model as represented in Figure 2 which comprises two primary components: the structural model and the measurement model, each one with its construction rules. The inner model focuses on the relationships between the latent variables. The variables that explain other variables are marked as exogenous while constructs that act as target variables are considered endogenous. The model also includes error terms connected to the independent variables to account for the variance measurement uncaptured by the model. In the outer model, the focus shifts to the outer factors. Therefore, the measurement model includes the observed indicators and represents the relationship between constructs and their indicators.

Figure 1: PLS-SEM Model

Notation	Description
Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, Y_4	Latent variables
Y_1 and Y_2	Exogenous variables
Y_3 and Y_4	Endogenous variables
x_1 to x_5	Indicators for the exogenous latent variables Y_1 and Y_2
x_6 to x_{10}	Indicators for the endogenous latent variables Y_3 and Y_4
e_1, e_2, e_3, z_3, z_4	Error terms for the endogenous variables $x_3, x_4,$ and x_5

Source: (Hair, et al., 2022)

After defining the models, estimation is carried out in two distinct stages: calculating the construct scores associated with the latent variables and estimating the path coefficients that quantify the relationships between the indicators and constructs (Hair, et al., 2022). The computed scores, generated from the PLS algorithm, are used in the PLS predict algorithm (Evermann & Tate, 2016) where they undergo normalization processes. The performance of the algorithm and the predictive power of the model are evaluated against the LM benchmark values by running a list of Linear Regressions across all the pairs of dependent and independent variables, comparing the resulted errors (Galit Shmueli, et al., 2019).

4. Multiple Linear Regression

If the methods described in the previous chapter had the ability to model non-linear relationships, when it comes to Multiple Linear Regression, only linear relationships are being modelled, the connected elements being represented by a single continuous dependent variable and multiple independent variables (James, et al., 2013). The method extends Simple Linear Regression method by incorporating multiple predictors into a single model, reducing the risk of misleading results caused by separate models for each pair of variables. The standard form for a Multiple Linear Regression is written as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_p X_p + \epsilon \tag{5}$$

The regression beta coefficients $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p$ serve as slopes for each independent variable X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p , and ϵ is the residual error, representing unexplained variability and randomness in the model. The coefficients indicate the changes in Y associated with one-unit change in an independent variable, holding the rest constant. Once the regression coefficients β are estimated, the model can predict new outcomes by substituting the values of independent variables into the regression equation. The accuracy of the model depends on how effectively the independent variables explain the variability in the dependent variable, with more accurate predictions leading to smaller residual errors.

5. Comparative Capabilities of MLR, PLS-SEM, GRF

After setting the theoretical framework which highlighted the principles of MLR, PLS-SEM, and GRF, their capabilities are reviewed and analyzed in terms of input data types, relationship assumptions and modeling requirements. All these methods aim to predict outcomes based on input variables, but they differ significantly in terms of assumptions, adaptability, and capacity to capture intricate patterns, when it comes to causal inference.

Renowned for its ease of use and interpretability, Multiple Linear Regression operates under the assumption that relationships between the dependent variable and the independent variables are linear, restricting its applications to specific contexts. The idea that the predictors are independent of one another, referred to as multicollinearity is a condition to which MLR models are particularly sensitive. This result is caused by the fact that real-world data often does not satisfy this requirement. Despite these limitations, MLR remains a favored method in predictive modeling, due to its high interpretability obtained through the presence of its coefficients, which represent clear indicators of the magnitude of influence each predictor exerts on the outcome. However, the ease of implementation advantage comes at the cost of flexibility as MLR is not suitable for handling non-linear relationships. Even if MLR is an effective approach for predictive modeling, it does not come with a robust framework for causal inference that sets estimating the impact of an intervention or a treatment as primary goal. In return, it assumes static relationships without accounting for treatments or heterogeneous effects.

Conversely, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) handles the previous limitation as it extends beyond the linear assumptions imposed by MLR, providing additional capabilities of modeling complex relationship between observed variables and multifaceted constructs. In comparison with MLR, PLS-SEM comes with increased robustness to multicollinearity through the latent constructs that can condense highly correlated indicators into composite variables. As a result, it delivers more stable and meaningful model estimates. PLS-SEM exhibits limited non-linearity, as it follows predefined patterns according to a general schema, compared to other techniques which manage purely non-linear interactions. In terms of integrated frameworks, PLS-SEM is mostly restricted to model associations rather than causal relationships. Although it can indicate possible paths of influence between variables, it does not come with instruments for calculating the effects of treatments or interventions, particularly in cases where the impact varies among subgroups in the data.

The novel approach, Generalized Random Forest (GRF) appears as a significant leap in the field of causal inference alongside predictive modeling, outstanding in handling non-linear relationships and complex interactions, while also estimating heterogeneous treatment effects. The assumptions over the functional form of relationships between variables that were associated to the previous methodologies are no longer mandated as GRF is a non-parametric technique that can handle highly intricate relationships of various types. By virtue of the feature of estimating heterogeneous treatment effects, GRF is especially well-suited for causal inference since it can quantify the effects of different treatments in a variety of context in addition to predicting outcomes. Its non-linear structure allows it to identify interactions and dependencies between variables that would remain hidden in traditional approaches modeling.

Even though the method brings significant improvements for predictive modeling as well as for causal inference, it still has certain limitations that generally revolves around its high computation complexity. This drawback was not encountered for the two traditional approaches, GRF demonstrating its shortcomings in this regard, yet offering the advantage of increased interpretability, model construction and tree-based training framework.

6. Results and Discussions

This section summarizes the results obtained by applying the described methodologies across the three different datasets. The findings are presented for each pair of dataset and technique to provide a focused perspective incorporating variable importance, predictive accuracy and general methodological insights. To compare the predictive capabilities of MLR, PLS-SEM, and GRF methods and observe their technical and practical differences, the analysis is conducted using the corresponding packages within the R Studio programming environment: modelr,

(Wickham, 2023), seminr (Ray, et al., 2024), grf (Tibshirani, et al., 2024). To validate the empirical robustness of the findings, benchmark datasets commonly used in PLS-SEM research are selected:

- **TAM (Technology Acceptance Model):**
Source: Saudi Arabia, 1,190 observations (Davis, et al., 1989)
Focus: Tracking technology usage tendencies within the general scope of computer usage
- **CUSL (Corporate Reputation Model):**
Source: German cell phone industry, 344 observations (Eberl & Schwaiger, 2005)
Focus: Exploring corporate reputation and financial performance
- **UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology)** (Venkatesh, et al., 2012) (Venkatesh, et al., 2003):
Source: South Korea, 397 observations (Song, et al., 2020)
Focus: Technology acceptance with two groups - users and non-users of cloud storage services

The structure of the datasets is presented in Table 2 where the target variable is displayed into a dedicated column, the rest comprising the independent variables with their specific notations and corresponding concepts. To explore the new functions introduced by GRF, one of the selected datasets enables the exploration of the primary feature of the technique: capturing heterogeneity while boosting representativity and segmentation of the data. The UTAUT dataset segregates two different groups according cloud computing usage, the population being divided by this measure, resulting in one category of users which utilize public cloud storage services and one of non-users who are unacquainted with this particular practice. This separation into multiple groups facilitates heterogeneity assessment through GRF methodology and its inherent particularities.

Table 2: Datasets Structure

Source Dataset	Independent Variables	Dependent Variable
TAM	USEF - PERCEIVED USEFULNESS EOU - PERCEIVED EASE OF USE ATT - ATTITUDE TOWARD USING BI - BEHAVIORAL INTENTION OF USE	USE - ACTUAL SYSTEM USE
CORP	ATTR - ATTRACTIVENESS COMP - COMPETENCE CSOR - CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY CUSA - CUSTOMER SATISFACTION LIKE - LIKABILITY PERF - PERFORMANCE QUAL - QUALITY	CUSL - CUSTOMER LOYALTY
UTAUT	PE - PERFORMANCE EXPECTANCY EE - EFFORT EXPECTANCY SI - SOCIAL INFLUENCE HM - HEDONIC MOTIVATION HA - HABIT	BI - BEHAVIORAL INTENTION

6.1 TAM Dataset

GRF Results

GRF consistently identifies Perceived Ease of Use (EOU3) as the most important feature across the dependent variables, suggesting that individuals are more likely to engage with a system if they find it easy to use, a strong relationship between the comfort of using a technology and the actual usage being indicated. Attitude Toward Using (ATT) and Behavioral Intention (BI) also appear frequently over the iterations, highlighting their importance across the target variable. This suggests that as users gain more experience, their personal feelings and evaluations about the technology take precedence over other factors. The top five most important variables revealed interesting findings. Taking a broader view on the results across the entire USE construct, out of 20 entries, the most frequent construct was ATT with 10 appearances, followed by 6 entries of EOU, 3 of BI and USEF which has appeared a single time. An intriguing observation is that even if general summary identified ATT as a frequent construct, out of the 4 predictors of USE, 3 of them consistently showed that EOU3 is the most important variable, even if other indicators of the same construct were rarely present.

Table 3: GRF Results – TAM

USE 1		USE 2		USE 3		USE 4	
0.190984521	EOU3	0.22619854	EOU3	0.288688530	EOU3	0.16482993	ATT1
0.108683800	BI3	0.09610759	BI3	0.163185144	ATT1	0.130183402	EOU3
0.101446035	ATT4	0.08014789	ATT3	0.080834855	ATT3	0.129751485	ATT2
0.085582231	EOU2	0.07595054	USEF4	0.077243209	ATT4	0.105385051	ATT3
0.065036577	ATT1	0.07086779	BI1	0.064569147	ATT5	0.069371706	EOU2

MLR Results

MLR results align partially with GRF findings, the method indicating Behavioral Intention (BI3) and Perceived Ease of Use (EOU3) as significant factors. The techniques shared the most important predictor, the differences arising when the importance of ATT construct has been replaced by USEF construct, a variable which did not attain a high degree of relevance when GRF was used.

Table 4: MLR Results – TAM

<i>Variable</i>	<i>P-value</i>	*	<i>P-value</i>	*		<i>P-value</i>	*	<i>P-value</i>	*
<i>USEF1</i>	0.00131	**	0.04326	*		0.58100		0.9699	
<i>USEF2</i>	0.13830		0.59706			0.21883		0.0465	*
<i>USEF3</i>	0.88899		0.22479			0.53874		0.3920	
<i>USEF4</i>	0.53183		0.02529	*		0.23726		0.1641	
<i>USEF5</i>	0.23799		0.02054	*		0.01551	*	0.0500	.
<i>EOU1</i>	0.00783	**	0.18098			0.61392		0.4384	
<i>EOU2</i>	0.16851		0.46896			0.32592		0.3507	
<i>EOU3</i>	5.23e-05	***	8.4e-06	***		0.00080	***	0.0699	.
<i>EOU4</i>	0.73640		0.25423			0.77170		0.9194	
<i>EOU5</i>	0.18614		0.68201			0.09097	.	0.2382	
<i>BI1</i>	0.20834		0.71224			0.35151		0.7536	
<i>BI2</i>	0.00651	**	0.08418	.		0.00881	**	0.0469	*
<i>BI3</i>	0.00618	**	0.00262	**		0.00451	**	0.2119	
<i>ATT1</i>	0.13634		0.76164			0.69791		0.2284	
<i>ATT2</i>	0.88317		0.16569			0.93081		0.4079	
<i>ATT3</i>	0.16046		0.02828	*		0.08829	.	0.3544	
<i>ATT4</i>	0.11148		0.23917			0.33737		0.8860	
<i>ATT5</i>	0.82198		0.94000			0.60623		0.7236	

PLS-SEM Results

PLS-SEM reconfirms GRF findings as the most relevant variable is yet again ATT, while keeping EOU as a significant predictor. The absolute value of EOU is very close to that of USEF construct which showed high importance in the Multiple Linear Regression method, but barely appeared when using GRF.

Table 5: PLS-SEM Total Effects - TAM

	EOU	USEF	ATT	BI	USE
EOU	0	0.500	0.410	0.302	0.179
USEF	0	0	0.276	0.509	0.171
ATT	0	0	0	0.174	0.345

	EOU	USEF	ATT	BI	USE
BI	0	0	0	0	0.164
USE	0	0	0	0	0

6.2 Corporate Reputation Dataset

GRF Results

GRF managed to identify a common most influential variable for each of these dependent variables, indicating robustness in determining variable importance. Specifically, “CUSA” depicting Customer Satisfaction became the variable that showed the highest value for Mean Decrease in Impurity across all the three dependent variables. This finding showed that customer loyalty is influenced by the extent to which the expectations and needs of customers are met. A higher level of satisfaction comes with a loyal potential customer, as highlighted by the entire list of dependent variables, which picked CUSA in the first position, a single-item construct measured by a unique indicator.

Table 6: GRF Results – CORP

CUSL1		CUSL2		CUSL3	
0.248101836	cusa	0.330369788	cusa	0.364074557	cusa
0.083780390	like 1	0.094890400	like 2	0.079404630	qual 3
0.072419278	qual 6	0.083763204	qual 5	0.071924286	like 3
0.070943636	qual 5	0.070079506	qual 3	0.071067075	like 1
0.047817580	comp 1	0.068817592	like 1	0.060469278	qual 5

MLR Results

The status of the most influential variable of “CUSA” persists when applying Multiple Linear Regression, as it is associated with low p-values. Contrasts become more noticeable when examining the rest important variables which exhibit lower significance. The results diverge for each dependent variable. For instance, when the dependent variable is CUSL1, the only notable indicators are LIKE1 and ATT1, with additional mentions of limited QUAL entries. CUSL2 reveals representatives for LIKE and CSOR, variables that were not reported by the GRF methodology. The appearance of Corporate Social Responsibility suggests that customer loyalty can be influenced by the company’s commitment to ethical practices and contributions to societal welfare. When the dependent variable switches to CUSL3, CSOR reappears as a representative variable.

Table 7: MLR Results - CORP

Variable	P-value	*	P-value	*	P-value	*
comp_1	0.088733		0.29358		0.5143	
comp_2	0.084741		0.83049		0.8484	
comp_3	0.084902	.	0.13622		0.7277	
like_1	0.083534	*	0.43269		0.4987	
like_2	0.063336		0.00400	**	0.3998	
like_3	0.061017		0.32041		0.1273	
cusa	0.091362	***	7.77e-11	***	2.29e-13	***
csor_1	0.070970		0.85985		0.8955	
csor_2	0.060578		0.00421	**	0.5953	
csor_3	0.080752		0.12218		0.0415	*
csor_4	0.075246		0.52531		0.1487	
csor_5	0.076729		0.62949		0.2803	
attr_1	0.071783		0.09266	.	0.8013	
attr_2	0.042555	*	0.95683		0.3633	

Variable	P-value	*	P-value	*	P-value	*
attr_3	0.078112		0.96971		0.8635	
perf_1	0.085453		0.31939		0.3273	
perf_2	0.080004		0.22909		0.8279	
perf_3	0.064789		0.42578		0.6459	
perf_4	0.075414		0.24722		0.3045	
perf_5	0.070912		0.87659		0.5888	
qual_1	0.087222		0.59779		0.7130	
qual_2	0.080807		0.04349	*	0.0802	.
qual_3	0.082892		0.21202		0.0530	.
qual_4	0.081555		0.63202		0.5171	
qual_5	0.086066		0.78394		0.8356	
qual_6	0.086850	.	0.27311		0.9029	
qual_7	0.070804		0.85654		0.0287	*
qual_8	0.071686	.	0.60405		0.6713	

PLS-SEM Results

The ascendancy of the most important variable shifts upon applying PLS-SEM methodology. In this case, LIKE variable takes the lead position, displacing CUSA, which assumes a second position. As anticipated, QUAL remains a significant factor, consistently holding a top position across both GRF and MLR analyses.

Table 8: PLS-SEM Total Effects - CORP

	QUAL	PERF	CSOR	ATTR	COMP	LIKE	CUSA	CUSL
QUAL	0	0	0	0	0.111	0.458	0.250	0.360
PERF	0	0	0	0	0.929	0.123	0.010	0.189
CSOR	0	0	0	0	0.008	0.095	0.050	0.078
ATTR	0	0	0	0	0.096	0.456	0.236	0.378
COMP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.060	0.096
LIKE	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.531	0.809
CUSA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.498

6.3 UTAUT Dataset

MLR Results

After running the regressions on UTAUT dataset, it was found that only a limited number of variables have a true influence over the target, leading to the rejection of the list of null hypotheses. HA4 (Habit) and PE1 (Performance Expectancy) variables returned small p-values across all the three features: BI1 B2 B3 (Behavioral Intention). The variables representing the same concept of Habit and Performed Expectancy were associated in general with larger p-values, the only features paired with a sufficiently low p-value being HA3 and HA1. Thus, habit is elevated in the position of the most relevant factor for Behavioral Intention, representing the degree to which individuals tend to automatically use the technology as a result of learning. Even if not all composites of Performance Expectancy were marked as important, the factor is considered sufficiently relevant for the target variable.

Table 9: MLR Results – UTAUT

Variable	P-value	*	P-value	*	P-value	*
PE1	0.0171	*	0.00392	**	0.000938	***
PE2	0.3397		0.90428		0.162382	
PE3	0.3886		0.20429		0.265242	
PE4	0.2217		0.76385		0.217045	
EE1	0.7389		0.97979		0.977103	
EE2	0.4068		0.18277		0.858735	
EE3	0.0883	.	0.11935		0.023003	*
EE4	0.3051		0.30981		0.989262	
SI1	0.4784		0.90057		0.349071	
SI2	0.7753		0.34153		0.853801	
SI3	0.9580		0.09509	.	0.122248	
HM1	0.2411		0.56277		0.411472	
HM2	0.4513		0.85525		0.971225	
HM3	0.6123		0.09914	.	0.441980	
HA1	0.1524		0.13708		0.097193	.
HA2	0.1340		0.15586		0.847455	
HA3	0.7967		0.00271	**	0.177541	
HA4	2.75e-05	***	0.00136	**	2.55e-07	***

PLS-SEM Results

PLS-SEM confirms the previous findings, the highest path coefficients being associated with the relevant predictors returned by MLR. Habit remains the most important predictor, being succeeded by expectancy in terms of effort and performance. This reveals that the ease of use and the expected results complement habitual behavior in shaping intentions.

Table 10: PLS-SEM Total Effects - UTAUT

	BI
PE	0.207797612045364
EE	0.137735473983608
SI	0.0549203963086736
HM	0.12660201609164
HA	0.482390357758873

GRF Results

It comes as no surprise that Habit, Performance Expectancy, and Effort Expectancy once again emerge as the top three important variables when switching to the GRF method. For all the dependent variables, representatives of HA feature were consistently returned, with HA4 occupying the anticipated first positions. Effort Expectancy and Performance Expectancy are placed on the next positions, while the other variables indicate lower values compared to the top identified ones. The three methods properly marked the shared universal predictor underscoring its role in behavioral intention.

Table 11: GRF Results - UTAUT

BI1		BI2		BI3	
00.261873469	HA4	0.54116633	HA4	0.427059393	HA4
00.161877236	HA3	0.09082203	HA1	0.170902037	EE3
0.121014383	PE1	0.06427759	HA3	0.065974140	PE1
0.102441877	EE3	0.03850058	SI3	0.043666454	HA3
0.043740959	HM1	0.03030626	HM1	0.038236850	HM1
0.040640477	EE2	0.02893040	PE4	0.034687885	EE1

6.4 Treatment Integration

The dataset incorporates a variable for treatment with categorical values of 1 and 0, denoting Yes and No classes, associated with individuals who frequently use public cloud storage services and those categorized as non-users. Thus, it is worthwhile to explore regression models that include the interaction between treatment and each independent variable. In this approach, the dependent variable, one instance of the BI construct remains constant in each iteration, while the independent indicators are adjusted to include their interaction with the treatment variable. The results including the list of the Multiple Regressions with the specific p-values are summarized in Table 12. The lowest p-value is encountered for the interaction between SI (Social Influence) construct and the treatment variable: SI2:0.000145, SI3:0.00259, SI1:0.00103, proving that there is a strong relationship between the Behavioral Intention and the interaction between the Social Influence and the status of a user regarding cloud storage usage. Social influence arises as the sole construct linked to low p-values across all its representative indicators. The second variable that stands out as influent through treatment interaction is Hedonic Motivation, as 2 out of 3 indicators returned low enough p-values. Other indicators, such as Effort Expectancy, Habit and Performance Expectancy showed some favorable results through at least one indicator each, but their consistency is weaker compared to the other independent variables. Habitual practices of an individual in formal and working contexts, paired with the utilization of cloud storage services have an impact in the enhancement of technological behavioral intentions. The compelling finding is centred on Social Influence construct that garnered attention only in the case in which the interaction with the treatment status was included. In contrast, when the standard Regressions with no interaction term were performed, it did not appear in the top of the influential variables.

Table 12: MLR Results - UTAUT Treatment

Feature:Interaction	P-value
PE1:DT	0.00406 **
PE2:DT	0.1709
PE3:DT	0.30917
PE4:DT	0.26288
EE1:DT	0.1869
EE2:DT	0.14465
EE3:DT	0.046004 *
EE4:DT	0.553
SI1:DT	0.00103 **
SI2:DT	0.000145 ***
SI3:DT1	0.00259 **
HM1:DT	0.048723 *
HM2:DT	0.264983
HM3:DT	0.00563 **
HA:DT	0.0865 .
HA2:DT	0.0163 *

Feature:Interaction	P-value
HA3:DT	0.28392
HA4:DT	0.31687

GRF Causal Forest - Variable Importance

Following the results of the variable importance functionality, it can be observed that notable disparities came out when treatment is included. The variable that gains importance is Social Influence, aligning with findings for the regressions with interaction term methodology. This points out that when the status of cloud services usage is considered, the social characteristics that can be resulted from technological usage are more important in drawing behavioral intention than those related to habits. However, the key construct, Habit, identified with the help of previous Regression Forest models, retained its relevance in the variable importance ranking of causal forests, the similarities being noticed also for Hedonic Motivation and Performance Expectancy. The variable that appeared to diminish in importance is the Effort Expectancy, suggesting that if the individuals have already the user status, they tend to omit the perceived effort. The reason may be the familiarity with tools and the technical implications, which in turn influence their intention to continue using the services.

Table 13: GRF Results - UTAUT Treatment

BI1		BI2		BI3	
0.18193133	SI2	0.15795187	SI1	0.07786564	PE4
0.17282287	SI3	0.11746639	SI3	0.06652620	SI3
0.09962170	SI1	0.09800577	HA1	0.06587571	PE2
0.08240940	HM3	0.09377856	SI2	0.06288236	HA2
0.06414397	HA3	0.07326276	PE4	0.06285480	SI2
0.06181762	HA2	0.06657764	HM3	0.05686810	SI1

6.5 Variable Importance

In terms of variable importance, the three methodologies involved in this study provided similar results across all the datasets, indicating that variations in methodology do not notably affect the identification of feature influence on the target variable. Table 14 comprises similar ordered lists, irrespective of the methodology employed, emphasizing the robustness of the performed analysis.

Table 14: GRF Variable Importance

Dataset	Method	Variable Importance
TAM	PLS-SEM	ATT, EOU, USEF
	GRF	ATT, EOU, BI
	ML	EOU, USEF, BI
CORP	PLS-SEM	LIKE, CUSA, QUAL
	GRF	CUSA, LIKE, QUAL
	ML	CUSA, CSOR, LIKE, QUAL
UTAUT2	PLS-SEM	HA, PE, EE
	GRF	HA, EE, PE
	ML	HA, PE, EE

6.6 Prediction Performance

The differences between the predicted and actual values were measured using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), a shared performance assessment metric, identified for GRF, ML and PLS-SEM. In general, the values obtained for all the methods fell within comparable ranges, indicating that the prediction phase was effectively conducted, with no significant discrepancies between methodologies. Notably, the lowest values of RMSE were returned for GRF methodology, as 7 out of the 10 cases were in favor of GRF, strengthening the robustness of this approach.

Table 15: GRF Prediction Performance

RMSE	PLS-SEM	GRF	ML
USE1	1.53	1.09	1.30

USE2	1.26	0.78	0.96
USE3	1.43	1.16	1.25
USE4	2.16	1.97	2.27

RMSE	PLS-SEM	GRF	ML
CUSL1	1.25	1.16	1.06
CUSL2	1.26	1.33	1.08
CUSL3	1.29	1.51	1.22

RMSE	PLS-SEM	GRF	ML
B1	0.99	0.75	0.91
B2	0.88	0.72	0.86
B3	0.96	0.73	0.88

7. GRF Findings

The application of Generalized Random Forest provided insightful results into how key features affect the Behavioral Intention over the technology usage in the context of cloud storage services as a treatment variable by virtue of its particular functionalities regarding causality and heterogeneity. Variable importance findings were consistent across both Regression and Causal Forests, presenting Habit, Hedonic Motivation, and Performance Expectancy as important predictors of Behavioral Intention. Causal Forest training returned differentiated responses tailored to the specific subgroups, shedding light on patterns and conclusions that would have been more difficult to capture using traditional methods. When distinguishing between users and non-users, knowing in advance in which category an individual falls in, social influence linked with the software usage become the pivotal factor. This suggested that social dynamics has an essential role for shaping behavioral intention when the status of an individual as a cloud service user is also considered.

The results are consistent with the study conclusion from which the UTAUT dataset was retrieved (Song, et al., 2020) as the authors applied PLS-SEM method on two distinct parts of the dataset, according to the user status. The results indicated that the usage of technology was significantly impacted by social influence in the case of non-users, demonstrating the validity of GRF Method. Another phenomenon observed only when the treatment is integrated into the analysis is that Effort Expectancy loses significance in predicting the target variable. This suggests that individuals which are already comfortable with cloud technologies will not consider the perceived effort as a relevant factor for the usage decision, likely due to their increased familiarity with the tools. GRF method provided valuable insights into the heterogeneity of treatment effects and revealed patterns that would have been challenging to capture without its integration. The performed models simultaneously returned low error rates, highlighting the capabilities of GRF in uncovering complex relationships within the data.

8. Conclusions

This paper introduced Generalized Random Forest (GRF) as a compelling alternative to traditional predictive modeling methods like Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). GRF sets itself apart from traditional methods through its capabilities of handling non-linear relationships and heterogeneous data, emerging as a technique well-suited for handling complex data scenarios, where conventional techniques tend to encounter limitations. Alongside its predictive power, robustness, enhanced interpretability, and advanced modeling techniques, GRF eliminated the need for manual input in determining a list of relevant variables for the target feature, providing an automated process for returning variable importance which allows for more in-depth insights into the contribution of each predictor, further enhancing the interpretability and clarity of the outcomes returned by the models.

Despite the continued relevance of MLR and PLS-SEM for specific research problems related to prediction and determining the influence of variables, GRF provides significant functionalities and advancements, especially where non-linear relationships, treatment introduction, causal inference and subgroup effects become critical. The findings extracted with practical experiments indicated that the dependence on the chosen metric is minimal as even if some variations are present, the main tendencies and patterns of the relevant variables remain consistent across the studied methodologies. GRF provided novel insights regarding patters within the treated population, while keeping the primary conclusions drawn from the rest of methodologies. The performance evaluation across the three techniques showed that GRF yielded the smallest values for RMSE metric in the vast majority of cases.

GRF enhances applied economic research by enabling the measurement of the impact of interventions on different population segments, moving away from simply average effects, employing data-driven heterogeneity and

uncovering more nuanced behavioral details compared to those captured with conventional models. Along with offering detailed analyses in labor, consumer and health economics or behavioral finance, its integration enhances causal reasoning in observational studies and improves predictive accuracy. These advanced features enable GRF to facilitate the study of a wide variety of real-world issues which have traditionally been approached with narrow and less flexible methods.

Declarations

Competing interests' declaration: No potential conflicts of interest identified.

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